

Analysis of Adult Literacy Teachers Training Programme In Punjab

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Abstract

Teachers not only build a structure for one field of life but also have tools and ideas to build up generation and strategies for every nation, society, and country. It must not be done without adult teachers training and not achieve the national goals or objectives of education. So this study has been designed to evaluate the adult literacy teachers training programme in the southern districts of the province of Punjab viz: Rahim Yar Khan and Bahawalpur. The study was quantitative in nature based on a survey of the opinions of the literacy teachers teaching in the aforesaid districts of Punjab. A questionnaire was used as a research tool for this study. To the tune of 300 teachers were selected at random as the sample of the study. The obtained data were analyzed applying frequency and percentage. It was found that the literacy teachers of these districts had the desire to be trained in a very comprehensive way. Literacy teachers should be given an incentive for effective training. Furthermore, the recommendations and suggestions were made on the basis of these findings

Keywords: *Adult education, literacy, adult literacy, literacy teachers, training programs*

Introduction

Education is an essential tool for the progress of any country, society .and state. At the individual level, it is an activity or a process which transforms the behavior of a person from instinctive behavior to human behavior. Education gives a man a new shape. It is a training of people for fulfilling the responsibilities of adult life. Animals are also trained, but in their training, the purpose is not well defined, as they are not human beings. Education develops in a man thinking and reasoning power in order to enable him to understand the occasion when he is faced with the pressing problems of the home, community, and the world. It is also the training of eye and mind. Provision of education is necessary so that the individual should make correct responses to the problems and the opportunities of life. Responses are of two kinds: physical and mental. Education is also the training of the intellect, body, and spirit. It is training that generates co-operation, love, and sympathy. It is the training to enable man to give the correct response to environmental conditions.

The teacher should be trained in the most suitable and effective way. He must be efficient and capable of presenting his information by the right method. It is very important to see how many trained teachers are required in the adult literacy program. After this assessment and training, we will be able to provide the required teacher for the adult literacy project and will be able to get these benefits.

The social, moral, physical, psychological training of the teachers should be given in the right way. The teaching learning process should be continued in the best manner. The better results of training will be produced. The training of teachers means to impart such technical skills to people by which they may do the duty of an effective teacher in the easiest way. All those activities that make an individual a complete teacher should also be included in this category. The teacher should be assigned the different stages of their adult students age and their total requirements so far to make the order of their teaching Program. Islam gives much importance to the teaching profession, as the teacher is the medium of spreading and preaching Islam and peace. Adult literacy teachers training has become a major issue in different countries of the world. Therefore, the need to adopt the best teacher training system for changing education environment has become one of the reform initiatives. Keeping in view the importance of teachers training this research will

highlight the need of trainers, policymakers, and academics to take account of the two ways: nature of the relationship between teacher training and the education.

Training

The idea of training is most usually associated with preparing someone for performing. Rao. D.B. (2001) opines in this way: “Training is provided for teachers to update their knowledge of content, methods of teaching, and new development in the curriculum.” In other words, it is very close to what some people define as the concept of training. So training here is a fully learning task by experiment. The concept of training is most usually related to preparing someone to do his work successfully in his work setting.

Goldstein and Gessner (1988) pointed out: Training is the systemic acquisition of skills, rules, concept or attitude that result in improved performance in the work situation. In some of these instances, such as direct on the job, the training occurs in a place far removed from the actual work site such as a classroom. (p-43). Training is said to be an activity for improving the quality of a person in every walk of life. This term is specially defined and explained in Glossary (1971) training has been defined as. “Systematic, development of attitude, knowledge, skill, behavior patterns required by an individual in order to perform a given job of the task adequately. The quality of education depends on the quality of teaches. The studies in teacher’s effectiveness have found that quality of teachers training Programs plays an effective role in building up effective teachers. According to Venkataich S. (2000), Adult Literacy Teachers Training is interpreted as Training for adult education should include all of these aspects: skill, knowledge understanding and personal attitude which are relevant to the various functions taking into account the general background against which adult education takes place. (p-34). Kamp. Di. (2001) Opines that: In the beginning, a trainer concentrated on those two areas of skills, giving, people a formula for the preparation of training materials and developing their ability to produce a variety of teaching aids.

Roger B & Jim C. (2000) points out about the training that: A planned and systematic effort to modify or develop knowledge / skill attitude through learning experience, to achieve effective performance in an activity or range of activities, it’s purpose, in the works situation, is to enable an individual to acquire abilities in order that he or she can perform a given task or job (p-I) adequately.

History of Ault Literacy Teachers Training

The social, economic, political and educational conditions have changed a lot on a global level, but no significant improvement has taken place in adult literacy teachers training that has been one of the tildest and most respected professions in the world. Kamp. Di. (2001) Opines that: In the beginning, a trainer concentrated on those two areas of skills, giving, people a formula for the preparation of training materials and developing their ability to produce a variety of teaching aids. Smith M.R. (1970) refers adult literacy teachers training in his words: “Adult education of the world confederation of organizations pf the teaching profession conducted an international workshop in Korea on “the Role of Teacher’s Organization in Adult Literacy Education.”

Training for Formal and Non-Formal Education Teachers

The training of teachers means to impart them such skills by which they may do the duty of effective teaching. In a straight way, these activities by which an individual may understand learners are also included in the training of teachers. They may be aware of the different stages of their age and their total requirement so to make the order of their teaching program. Non-formal schools have begun to play a dramatic role in education. These schools have long been ignored in Pakistan. So important a role have they that according to the report, human development in south Asia 1998, any plan to extend universal primary education in Pakistan by the year 2003 will not be successful unless there is a major stress on non-formal education.

The significance of the Study

Literacy is a serious challenge for the third world. Pakistan also wants to teach her uneducated persons. Untrained teachers are often responsible for low literacy and high dropout rate. The teacher without training is like a tree that can’t bring forth fruit. So without training, a teacher is just like an illiterate person and

can't teach students. He often makes the students bored. Therefore, learners don't take an interest. An untrained teacher does not know which method of teaching is good to teach and how to plan a lesson and deal with different I.Q. level learners in the class. When he does not know it, he can't prepare a good lesson, and students leave the literacy center. Most of the people join the teaching profession without their willingness, so they don't take an interest in teaching. I selected this topic because of its importance.

Statement of the Problem

The main area of the present study is “Analysis of Adult Literacy Teachers Training Programs for Adult Literacy Teachers.”

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To evaluate the current adult literacy teachers training programs.
2. To analyze the method of teaching & skill of adult literacy teachers.

Research Questions

The following research questions were framed to be answered:

1. Are the literacy teachers training programs satisfied the teacher's concerns?
2. What are the methods and skills provided in literacy teachers training programs?

Methods and procedures of the study

The present study was quantitative in nature that was based on a survey of the opinions of the literacy teachers of the districts of Rahim Yar Khan and Bahawal Pur of the province of Punjab.

Population and Sampling of the study

Literacy teachers of the province of Punjab were the population of the study. Punjab consisted of 36 districts in total. The researcher selected two districts viz: Rahim Yar Khan and Bahawal Pur district because of the remote and backward areas of the province. The researcher selected 300 literacy teachers at random. From which 150 literacy teachers belonged to Rahim Yar Khan and 150 were from Bahawal Pur having the minimum experience of three months from the NCHD (National Commission for Human Development) and PLC (PLC Commission) literacy centers.

Instrumentation

In the present study, only “Questionnaire” was used as a tool for data collection because of the shortage of time. A questionnaire was developed to collect data from Adult Literacy Teachers. The questionnaire had 21 questions prepared for the Adult Literacy Teachers. The tool was validated by the experts of the area before administration.

Tool administration and Data Collection

The questionnaire prepared for the present research was distributed among the respondents by the researcher himself. Because this was the most suitable way of distribution. In this way, the researcher could explain the main aspects and the objectives of research in front of the respondents. 300 questionnaires were distributed to the Adult Literacy Teachers. The data for the present study was based on the information, comments, and suggestions received from the Adult Literacy Teachers. The researcher got Adult Literacy Teachers opinions through a questionnaire. The data was collected by administering, one questionnaire from Adult Literacy Teachers. To the tune of 100 (NCHD + PLC) Adult Literacy Teachers in Rahimyar Khan District and 109 Adult Literacy Teachers (NCHD + PLC) in Bahawalpur District male & female from rural and urban areas filled in the scale and 209 questionnaires were received from them. It means the rate of response of the Adult Literacy Teachers was 70%.

Table 1: Showing the rate if responses

Subject	Total No. of Respondents (NCHD)	Total No. of Respondents (PLC)	Total
Adult Literacy Teachers in Rahimyar Khan District.	65	35	100
Adult Literacy Teachers in Bahawalpur District.	90	19	109

Analysis of Data

The data collected through the questionnaire from Adult Literacy Teachers were put on graph paper for consolidation and statistical treatment for each item. Then the data were analyzed and interpreted in the light of the problem of the research. The percentage was calculated, and the ratio of responses was identified. The conclusions were drawn on the basis of the findings of the study. Some recommendations and suggestions have also been made for the solution of the problems identified through the present study. The information received from the Adult Literacy Teachers through questionnaire was analyzed that was shone as under:

Table 2: Showing the Ratio of Adult Literacy Teacher Training

DISTRICTS	Three	Five	Seven	Ten	Any other	Total
Frequency	40	12	08	03	02	65
NCH-RYK	62%	18%	12%	05%	03%	100%
Frequency	15	05	08	02	05	35
PLC-RYK	43%	14%	23%	6%	14%	100%
Overall	55%	17%	16%	05%	07%	100%
Frequency	22%	30%	14%	21%	03%	90%
NCH-BWP	25%	33%	16%	23%	03%	100%
Frequency	06%	05%	04%	02%	02%	19%
PLC-BWP	32%	26%	20%	11%	11%	100%
Overall	26%	32%	16%	21%	05%	100%

The above table shows that 62% NCHD District Rahimyar Khan teachers suggested that training should be in three days, 23% PLC District Rahimyar Khan teachers suggested seven days while in overall District Rahimyar Khan 55% teachers suggested that training should be in three days. It is clear from the above table and graph that three days teachers' training was the first priority of adult literacy teachers in District Rahimyar Khan. 33% NCI- {D District Bahawalpur teachers suggested that training should be in five days, 32% PLC District Bahawalpur teachers suggested three days while in overall District Bahawalpur 32% teachers suggested that training should be in three days. It is clear that five days teachers' training is the first priority of adult literacy teachers in District Bahawalpur.

Table 3: Showing the opinions regarding Training Workshop Hours

DISTRICTS	Four	Five	Six	Seven	Other	Total
Frequency	32	25	06	01	01	65
NCH-RYK	49%	38%	09%	02%	02%	100%
Frequency	14	11	08	01	01	35
PLC-RYK	40%	31%	23%	03%	03%	100%
Overall	46%	36%	14%	02%	02%	100%
Frequency	50%	22%	11%	08%	03%	100%
NCH-BWP	56%	22%	11%	08%	03%	100%
Frequency	16%	02	01	00	00	19
PLC-BWP	84%	11%	05%	00%	00%	100%
Overall	61%	20%	10%	06%	03%	100%

The above table shows that 49% NCHD District Rahimyar Khan teachers suggested that four hours workshop should be in teacher training, 40% PLC District Rahimya Khan teachers suggested that four hours workshop should be in teacher training while in overall District Rahimyar Khan 46% teachers suggested that four hours workshop should be in teachers training. It is clear from the above table and graph that four hours were the first priority of adult literacy teachers in District Rahimyar Khan. 56% NCHD District Bahawalpur teachers suggested that four hours workshop should be in teachers training, 84% PLC District Bahawalpur teachers suggested that four-hour workshop should be in teacher training while in overall District Rahimyar Khan 61% teachers suggested that four hours workshop should be in teachers training. It is clear from the above table and graph that four hours were the first priority of adult literacy teachers in District Bahawalpur.

Tale 4: Showing the opinions regarding Training Workshop Sessions

DISTRICTS	Two	Three	Four	Five	Other	Total
Frequency	39	15	04	05	02	65
NCH-RYK	60%	23%	06%	08%	03%	100%
Frequency	17	15	03	00	00	35
PLC-RYK	48%	43%	09%	00%	00%	100%
Overall	56%	30%	07%	05%	02%	100%
Frequency	56%	30%	07%	05%	02%	100%
NCH-BWP	68%	22%	07%	02%	01%	100%
Frequency	10	04	03	02	00	19
PLC-BWP	53%	21%	16%	10%	00%	100%
Overall	65%	22%	08%	04%	01%	100%

The above table shows that 60% NCHD District Rahimyar Khan teachers suggested that two session workshop should be in teacher training, 48% PLC District Rahimyar Khan teachers suggested that two session workshop should be in teacher training while in overall District Rahimyar Khan 56% teachers suggested that two session workshop should be in teachers training. It is clear from the above table and graph that two session workshop was the first priority of adult literacy teachers in District Rahimyar Khan. 68% NCHD District Bahawalpur teachers suggested that two session workshop should be in teachers training, 53% PLC District Bahawalpur teachers suggested that two session workshop should be in teacher training while in overall District Bahawalpur 65% teachers suggested that two session workshop should be

in teachers training. It is clear from the above table and graph that two sessions were the first priority of adult literacy teachers in District Bahawalpur.

Table 5: Showing the opinions regarding Training Workshop Remuneration

DISTRICTS	Rs.100/-	Rs.200/-	Rs.300/-	Other	Total
Frequency	25	19	16	05	65
NCH-RYK	38%	29%	25%	08%	100%
Frequency	08	10	16	01	35
PLC-RYK	23%	28%	46%	03%	100%
Overall	33%	29%	32%	06%	90
Frequency	29	25	30	06	90
NCH-BWP	32%	28%	33%	07%	100%
Frequency	04	08	05	02	19
PLC-BWP	21%	42%	26%	11%	100%
Overall	30%	30%	33%	07%	100%

The opinions of the adult literacy teachers were collected. The above table shows that 38% NCHD District Rahimyar Khan teachers suggested that Rs. 100/- remuneration should be given to each teacher in training, 46% PLC District Rahimyar Khan teachers suggested that Rs.300/- remuneration should be given to each teacher in training while in overall District Rahimyar Khan 33% teachers suggested that Rs. 100/- remuneration should be given to each teacher in training. It is clear from the above table and graph that Rs.300/- remuneration should be given to each teacher in training was the first priority of adult literacy teachers in District Rahimyar Khan 43% NCHD District Bahawalpur teachers suggested that Rs.300/- remuneration should be given to each teacher in training, 42% PLC District Bahawalpur teachers suggested that Rs.200/- remuneration should be given to each teacher in training while in overall District Bahawalpur 33% teachers suggested that Rs.300/- remuneration should be given to each teacher in training. It is clear from the above table and graph that Rs.200/- remuneration should be given for each teacher in training was the first priority of adult literacy teachers in District Bahawalpur.

Table 6: Showing the Problems hardship face by the teachers during in literacy center

DISTR ICTS	Lack of center facilities	Learner's absence	Difficulty learn to elder	Checking of male officers	Learnt to technical	The hesitation of learner's	Lack of charts	No answer	No, any difficulty	Many difficulties	Total
RYK	18%	33%	22%	00%	00%	00%	00%	07%	16%	04%	100%
(NCHD+PLC)	54%	19%	18%	00%	00%	00%	06%	00%	00%	03%	100%

The above table shows that 33% NCHD+PLC District Rahimyar Khan teachers said that learners' absence was a problem at in illiteracy center. It is clear from the above table and graph that teachers said that learners' absence was a problem at in literacy center was the priority of adult literacy teachers in District Rahimyar Khan.

54% NCHD+PLC District Bahawalpur teachers said that lack of physical facilities was a problem at a literacy center. It is clear from the above table and graph that lack of physical facilities were a problem at the literacy center was the first priority of adult literacy teachers in District Bahawalpur.

Findings

1. 62% NCHD District Rahimyar Khan teachers suggested that training should be in three days while overall District Rahimyar Khan 55% teachers suggested that training should be in three days and 33% NCHD District Bahawalpur teachers suggested that training should be in five days while overall District Bahawalpur 32% teachers suggested that training should be in three days.
2. 49% NCHD District Rahimyar Khan teachers suggested that four hours workshop should be in teachers training while in overall District Rahimyar Khan 46% teachers suggested that four hours workshop should be in teachers training and 84% PLC District Bahawalpur teachers suggested that four hours workshop should be in teachers training while in overall District Rahimyar Khan 61% teachers suggested that four hours workshop should be in teachers training.
3. 60% NCHD District Rahimyar Khan teachers suggested that two sessions workshop should be in teachers training while in overall District Rahimyar Khan 56% teachers suggested that two sessions workshop should be in teachers training and 68% NCHD District Bahawalpur teachers suggested that two sessions workshop should be in teachers training.
4. 46% PLC District Rahimyar Khan teachers suggested that Rs.300/- remuneration should be given to each teacher in training while in overall District Rahimyar Khan 33% teachers suggested that Rs.100/- remuneration should be given to each teacher in training and 42% PLC District Bahawalpur teachers suggested that Rs.200/- remuneration should be given for each teacher in training while in overall District Bahawalpur 33% teachers suggested that Rs.300/- remuneration should be given for each teacher in training.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, the following recommendations are made:

- Teachers training teachers should be set up after the gathering adult literacy teachers of three union councils or Mohall's local area.
- Adult Literacy teachers' pay should be increased from Rs. 1500/- to Rs3000/-
- Regularly and in time pay should be paid.
- Teacher training should consist of five days.
- Teacher training duration should be five hours daily.
- The teacher training session should be twice in a day.
- Master trainer should be trained, and he should know all teaching methods.

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